

D4.6: Implementation of R9 Sorting Game

WP4

Serious Games Interactive

Type of document: Other

Dissemination level: PU

Reviewers: Aclima, Zabala, FDEUSTO

Version	Date	Description of main changes	Author
1	28/11/2018		Susanne Husted (SGI)
2	14/12/2018	Annex added in table of contents	Susanne Husted (SGI)

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Executive summary

This delivery contains the following:

- A published version of the game Ways2Sort, available on [App Store](#) and [Google Play](#).
- A game manual describing all the features of the game and how to play it. See Annex A.

Short introduction to the game

Test your waste sorting knowledge and your ability to learn and remember which waste items belong where. Work on your high score by being faster and more accurate.

Ways2Sort aims to educate children on the importance of waste sorting and how to sort waste correctly. The game incorporates factual waste sorting data and methods from different municipalities, which makes it highly customizable and relevant for each individual municipality.

In the game, different waste items are presented to the player, who has to figure out which waste bin to put the items into. The player is introduced to different sorting types, e.g. residual waste, glass, biowaste etc., and different environments, e.g. kitchen, garden and kid's room.

Features

- 200 different waste items
- 6 environments/chapters
- Bonus levels at the end of each chapter with a different game mechanic to shake things up and test the player in new ways
- Encyclopaedia with an overview of all the sorting types and which waste items belong where
- Web editor which allows the municipalities who are part of the project to manage the sorting data used in the game
- Currently available in English, Spanish, Basque, Greek, Italian and Portuguese.

APPENDIXES OF
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ANNEX A: Ways2Sort Game Manual

Ways2Sort- short introduction

Go to <https://w4t.seriousgames.net/ways2sort/> for up-to-date information about the game and app download links.

The game teaches the user to sort waste correctly. ~200 waste items are included in the game, and the sorting rules correspond to the rules that actually apply in the given municipality.

Ways2Sort is a fun arcade-style game. The main target group is children aged 7-10 but can be enjoyed by everyone of age 4+.

Step-by-step guide

1. Create new user:

The first time you play the game, you have to start by creating a new user. Enter a username of your own choice, and choose your country and municipality. The language will automatically switch to the local language of the country you choose.

You're also asked to enter your gender and age (optional, but recommended, as it will be useful for the data analysis and research performed as part of the Waste4Think project).

Press arrow in lower left corner to continue.

Crea un nombre de usuario/a y selecciona tu país y municipio

NOMBRE DE USUARIO/A *

PAÍS *

MUNICIPIO *

GENERO **EDAD**

➔

2. Answer pre-game questionnaire:

Some questions are asked of the user before playing the game, to get a measure of the user's waste habits and attitude towards waste sorting.

The answers will be very helpful for the Waste4Think research, so please make sure to answer if possible.

The questionnaire can be skipped by pressing the Skip button.

CUESTIONARIO
Antes de jugar el juego, responde algunas preguntas.
¡Gracias por tu ayuda!

¿Cómo calificaría sus hábitos de clasificación de residuos?

Muy malos 1 2 3 4 5 6 Muy buenos

¿Qué importancia tiene para el manejo sostenible de los residuos para ti?

Poco 1 2 3 4 5 6 Mucho

¿Crees que cambiarás tus hábitos de clasificación de residuos después de jugar este juego?

No es muy probable 1 2 3 4 5 6 Muy probable

SALTA

3. Main menu:

The main menu gives you the following options:

- New Game/Continue Game - click here to start a new game or continue if you've played before.
- Sortindex - this is your encyclopedia on the waste items and sorting types that are included in the game.
- Settings - click here to access language selection, audio settings, user selection, and About page.

4. New/Continue Game:

When you select New/Continue Game, you'll go to the Level Selection screen. Here you can scroll through all the levels and chapters. As you play through each level, they will unlock and can later be accessed again through this screen.

Each chapter is a different location in or outside the home. Locations are 1) kitchen, 2) garden, 3) living room, 4) bathroom, 5) kid's room and 6) picnic.

Click on the level you want to play (Level 1 if you're starting a new game).

5. Level introduction:

This screen will be shown before each level. Here you get an overview of the sorting types that will be included in the level (listed horizontally at the top of the screen), as well as three examples of waste items that belong in this sorting type. This is simply to give the user a sense of what each sorting type is and what the corresponding waste bin looks like in the game.

You can look through all the sorting types by clicking on their icons.

A level can include up to five sorting types (starts at two and will increase as you play through the game).

Press the Play button to start playing the level.

6. Gameplay:

Waste items will spawn one at a time from the portal in the middle of the screen. If you have your audio turned on, a voiceover will say the name of the item when it spawns.

A timer counts down, and if it reaches zero, the item will disappear and you will get zero points for that item.

Drag the item to the bin/sorting type you think it belongs to. If you sort it correctly, you get plus points (10, 8 or 5, depending on the timer). If you sort it incorrectly, you'll get minus points (half of the current number, e.g. -5 points if the timer is in the green zone).

Note that it's worse to sort something incorrectly than it is to let the time run out. So taking your time to think is the best strategy.

If you sort five items correctly in a row, you'll get bonus points (the star behind the point counter fills up). If you continue your streak and get 10, 15, etc. correct in a row, you'll get increasingly more bonus points.

Difficulty: The difficulty level adapts slightly to the user's performance. When you make an error, the timer will go a bit slower for the next item. Conversely, if you sort an item correctly, the timer will go slightly faster next time. This is a "hidden" mechanic that will adjust the game to players of different ages/skill levels.

You'll be presented with five items from each sorting type. Once you've sorted all the items, the level is completed.

7. Level results:

You'll get an overview of how many items you sorted correctly in each sorting type. If you had no errors, you can move on directly to the next level by pressing the Play button. If you made mistakes, you will continue to a screen which shows you the sorting type that you made the most mistakes in, as well as the specific items you sorted incorrectly. Drag the items into the correct bin. Now you can continue to the next level, or press the Replay button to play the level again and try to improve your score.

8. Bonus level:

At the end of each chapter, there is a special bonus level which has a different gameplay than the regular levels. Now you're in the waste sorting plant where you have to help sort all the unsorted waste. Waste items will appear on the conveyor belt continuously. Drag the items to the bin you think is correct. If an item reaches the end of the conveyor belt, it will fall into the landfill or incinerator (depends on what your municipality has chosen as the end station).

Difficulty: Even more so than in the regular levels, the speed in the bonus level is adjusted to the player's performance. If the player is doing well, the belt will speed up gradually but significantly. The player will also get more plus points for each correct item when the speed is high. If the player is making many mistakes, the belt will slow down to give more time to think, but the player will also get less points.

9. Answer post-game questionnaire:

When you reach chapter 5, a second questionnaire will pop up. Here you're asked some questions about your enjoyment of the game and whether you feel you've learned anything.

The answers will be very helpful for the Waste4Think research, so please make sure to answer if possible.

The questionnaire can be skipped by pressing the Skip button.

10. Sortindex:

From the Main Menu, you can access the Sortindex.

Here, you'll see all the sorting types that are included in the game along with a short description.

Click on a sorting type to see which waste items belong to the type. Items that you've encountered in the game are shown fully. Items that you haven't encountered yet are shown only as a black silhouette. Go sort 'em all!

11. Settings:

From the Main Menu, you can access the Settings.

- **Language:** Here you can switch language. Be aware that the names of the sorting types and waste items depends on the country/municipality you chose when you created your user, and they won't change if you switch language.
- **Sounds:** Here you can adjust the volume of either all the sounds (master volume) or of the background music, sound effects, and waste item voiceover individually.

- Users: Here you can see a list of all the users created on your device, and you can switch between them. Switching to another user will set the game progression to whatever level that user had reached. You can create a new user by clicking the Create New User button.
- About: Here you can find credits for the game and some information about the Waste4Think project.

Comments from external reviewers 1

1.1. External reviewer 1

DATE: 29/11/2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?		X	2 The game manual does not follow the deliverables format of the project
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	X		5
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	X		5
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	X		5 The user manual is written in a very understandable way
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	X		5
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	X		5
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5 Screenshots of the manual should have a caption
Are the indexes correct?	X		5
Is the written English correct?	X		5
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?			There are no technical references
Glossary present in the document?		X	There is no Glossary

Name: Edurne Fernandez de Liger

Email: edurne@aclima.eus

Partner: Aclima

Comments from external reviewers 2

1.2. External reviewer 2

DATE: 11/12/2018

Issue	Yes	No	Score (1=low to 5=high)	Comments
Is the format of the document correct?	x		3	Although the deliverable is in the right format, the annex should follow a similar format
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5	
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		4	I would add the annex in the index
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		5	Isn't there a danish version of the app? If so, just make sure you mention it.
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		5	
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5	
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?		x	1	Not in the annex
Are the indexes correct?	x		5	
Is the written English correct?	x		5	
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		x	5	Not present, but not needed in my opinion.
Glossary present in the document?		x	5	No Glossary, but not need in my opinion.

Name: Joseba Merino

Email: jmerino@zabala.es

Partner: ZABALA

Comments from external reviewers 3

1.3. External reviewer 3

DATE: 14/12/2018

Issue	Score		Comments
	Yes	No	
Is the format of the document correct?	x		5
Does the format of the document meet the objectives of the work done?	x		5
Does the index of the document Collect precisely the tasks and issues that need to be reported?	x		5
Is the content of the document clear and well described?	x		5
Does the content of each section describe the advance done during the task development?	x		5
Does the content have sufficient Technical description to make clear the research and development performed?	x		5
Are all the figures and tables numerated and described?	X		5
Are the indexes correct?	X		5
Is the written English correct?	X		5
Main technical terms are correctly referenced?		X	5 Not needed
Glossary present in the document?		X	5 Not needed

Name: Oihane Kamara Esteban

Email: oihane.esteban@deusto.es

Partner: FDEUSTO